

Passive Geolocation of Mobile Subscribers Using a Single Base Station with Third Party Capture

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Abstract—In many densely populated environments, there is an abundance of base stations by which a mobile station may be passively geographically located (geolocated) using various techniques that require multiple base stations. Areas in which base station density is sparse may not possess the requisite number of base stations to perform such techniques and, therefore, require different methods by which to geolocate mobile stations. In this paper, we present a passive geolocation scheme that only requires observation of the initial ranging information exchange between a mobile station and a single base station in order to determine a position estimate for the mobile station. The scheme is specifically applied to the Worldwide Interoperability for Microwave Access (WiMAX) 4G standard. The method is validated through computer simulation and field experimentation in a WiMAX network.

Keywords—*geolocation; mobile wireless networks; 4G networks*

I. INTRODUCTION

The proliferation of Fourth Generation (4G) mobile wireless networks and mobile devices has led to the rapid development of numerous applications. Many of these new applications incorporate the mobile device location into their functionality, thereby increasing the demand for accurate mobile device position estimation, or geographic location (geolocation). Additionally, the trending shift toward mobile devices as the primary means of household voice communication places even more emphasis on mobile device geolocation in order to comply with government regulations for emergency response, such as E911.

In many densely populated environments, there is an abundance of base stations by which a mobile station may be passively geographically located using various techniques which require multiple base stations; however, areas in which base station density is sparse may not possess the requisite number of base stations to perform multi-base station techniques and, therefore, require the development of different methods by which to geolocate mobile stations.

This paper presents a time-of-arrival based method for the passive geolocation of a mobile station using observed

initial ranging information exchanged between the mobile station and a single base station. Specifically, we demonstrate a proof-of-concept through computer simulation and field experimentation in a WiMAX mobile wireless network

Mobile device position estimation techniques have been widely researched during the rise of mobile networks over the past two decades. A survey of different techniques including Received Signal Strength (RSS), Time-of-Arrival (TOA), Time Difference-of-Arrival, and Angle-of-Arrival (AoA) was presented in [1]. WiMAX geolocation methods utilizing TOA using timing adjust data extracted from the initial ranging exchange during network entry are examined in [2] and [3]; however, their efforts focused on accuracy improvement rather than deriving a position estimate using a minimal number of base stations. A single base station method using an array of three independent transducers to perform trilateration is proposed in [4]. This paper proposes a geolocation method that requires a single base station to communicate with the mobile station.

A method employing a collection device was proposed in [5] to combine propagation time with the unique RSS profiles created in an indoor environment to locate a radio frequency identification tag. The CELLO Consortium project report also contains a number of potential single base station geolocation techniques [6]. A method for single base station geolocation that relies solely on TOA measurements between a base station and mobile station is introduced in [7]. The TOA measurements are collected by a sensor that produces a position estimate relative to the position of the sensor. The work reported in this paper explores a geolocation method that requires minimal a priori information about the mobile network environment to generate a position estimate that is contingent only on TOA calculations.

The paper is organized as follows. Geolocation via timing adjust in WiMAX networks is discussed in Section II. The proposed scheme is outlined in Section III. Results of the experiments are presented in Section IV.

II. GEOLOCATION VIA TIMING ADJUST

A graphical representation of an OFDMA Time Division Duplex (TDD) frame used in the IEEE 802.16 standard can be seen in Figure 1 [8], [9]. Downlink and uplink traffic is scheduled as bursts using time-frequency combinations best suited to the channel conditions of each user. Notice the organization of the frame into the downlink and uplink subframes in addition to the Transmit-to-receive Transition Gap (TTG) and Receive-to-transmit Transition Gap (RTG) that separate the sub-frames [10].

Figure 1. Illustration of OFDMA frame with TDD operation from [9].

A. Ranging

During entry into the network, the mobile station transmission timing is not synchronized with the base station. Timing synchronization is achieved during the initial ranging process. First, the mobile station must listen for a ranging opportunity specified during each frame by the base station. Next, the mobile station transmits a code-division multiple access (CDMA) sequence during the time period in the uplink sub-frame allocated for initial ranging. The base station receives the CDMA sequence and sends time, power, and frequency adjustments back to the mobile station in a Range Response (RNG-RSP) message. The mobile station proceeds to adjust all required parameters, and the exchange repeats in order to validate that the mobile station is transmitting within the base station specified constraints and may enter the network [10].

The timing representing the round trip time instructs the mobile station to advance/delay its transmissions in order to become synchronized and is given in units of the sampling period. The timing adjust value can be calculated as

$$N_{TA} = \text{round} \left(d \frac{2F_s}{c} \right) \quad (1)$$

where d is the distance, c is the speed of light, and F_s is the sampling frequency [10].

B. Geolocation

The distance information inherent in the time adjust is also useful for TOA-based geolocation:

$$d = ct_{prop} \quad (2)$$

where t_{prop} is the propagation time. The distance in (2) can be thought of as the radius of a circle centered at the base station location. Given that the base station location is fixed, the mobile station must lie somewhere on a circle with a radius defined by the propagation time as given by [2], [3]

$$t_{prop} = \frac{1}{2F_s} (N_{TA} - N_{TA_bias}) \quad (3)$$

where N_{TA} is the timing adjust in the RNG-RSP message, N_{TA_bias} is the network timing adjust bias, and F_s is the sampling frequency. Substituting (3) into (2) yields the timing ring:

$$d = \frac{c}{2F_s} (N_{TA} - N_{TA_bias}) \quad (4)$$

Three timing rings derived from the timing adjusts of three independent base stations can lead to a single x-y position estimate for the mobile station in areas with constant wireless service from numerous base stations in close proximity. The position estimation error in this case is approximately 20 meters [2], [3].

III. SINGLE BASE STATION GEOLOCATION

Geolocation of a mobile station via the TOA method using time adjusts from two or more base stations is a relatively accurate and straightforward process as shown in [2], [3]. Sparsely populated and developing areas may not enjoy the same level of network saturation, and have only one base station to serve a large geographic area. This poses a unique problem for geolocation in these environments since the number of base stations required for multi-lateration techniques is not met; thus, we propose a method by which a mobile station may be passively geolocated using a single base station.

A. Proposed Scheme

The ranging information exchanged between a mobile station and a single base station will only generate a single timing ring resulting in a position ambiguity; thus, the general problem is to determine a method for generating an additional timing ring centered at a location other than that of the base station in order to disambiguate the position estimate. The passive generation of a timing ring requires some form of wireless capture equipment to be within range of the base station and mobile station to capture the ranging signals. This equipment provides a known location which can be used as the center of a timing ring. The task is then to determine the distance between the mobile station and the wireless capture equipment in order to determine the timing ring radius.

The IEEE 802.16-OFDMA TDD frame structure and the initial ranging process in conjunction with the location of the

base station and capture equipment provide enough information to successfully estimate the distance between the mobile station and wireless capture equipment. The wireless capture equipment need only record the initial CDMA sequence sent by the mobile station and the corresponding timing adjust within the RNG-RSP message issued by the base station. A graphical illustration of the general scenario can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2. General sparse environment geolocation scenario in WiMAX.

The timing ring associated with the capture equipment location and the timing ring associated with the base station location meet the minimum requirements of the geometric position estimation methods discussed in [2]; thus, a significantly less ambiguous position estimate can be determined for the mobile station. A schematic diagram of the proposed method can be seen in Figure 3. The capture equipment extracts the necessary information from the base station and mobile station transmissions and provides them as inputs to the post processing algorithm. The algorithm generates a position estimate, and the resulting reduction in position ambiguity can be seen in Figure 4. The blue circle represents the location of the base station to which the mobile station is attached, the red X represents the mobile station location, and the blue dashed line is the timing ring centered at the base station. The black triangle represents the location of the wireless capture equipment, the black dashed line is the timing centered at the capture equipment, and the green squares are the two possible fix locations. Additional disambiguation down to a single fix is possible if knowledge of the mobile station’s previous location is available.

B. Capture Requirements

Capturing the initial ranging message exchange between a mobile station and base station requires a certain amount of a priori information about the wireless network: channel bandwidth, frame duration, cyclic prefix, fast Fourier transform size, downlink to uplink symbol ratio, and RTG. Generally, all of these values are specified in the System Profile, which is periodically updated and released by the WiMAX Forum [8]. However, there are many possibilities for the downlink to uplink symbol ratio, so additional system specification analysis may be required to determine the value

for this parameter. Additionally, the distance between the base station and wireless capture equipment must be known.

Figure 3. Schematic of proposed single base station geolocation scheme.

Figure 4. Graphic of a timing ring from a single base station in conjunction with a timing ring from a capture location to reduce ambiguity.

Once successful air interface capture has been achieved, the inputs for the post processing algorithm must be collected. The start time of the first CDMA sequence, the start time of the frame in which the sequence occurred, and the corresponding RNG-RSP must be captured (see Figure 5). The RNG-RSP message contains the timing adjust needed to determine the distance between the base station and mobile station (−95 in this case).

C. Post Processing

The post processing algorithm accepts the captured inputs and steps backwards through the ranging process to estimate the original time at which the CDMA sequence was sent by the mobile station. The difference between the estimated time the sequence was sent and the time it was received is then converted to a distance from which the timing ring can be formed. We will use the variables t_{OL} and t_{IL} to denote each of these times, respectively.

Figure 5. Contents of the RNG-RSP message.

Much like the timing adjust bias associated with the network, the equipment used to capture the initial ranging messages may also have an associated timing bias [2], [3]. If that is found to be true, the equipment timing bias must be removed from the affected captured times in order to accurately estimate any timing throughout the process. The timing offset reference point is based on the frame structure the capture equipment receives on the downlink channel from the base station. Thus, when the mobile station, base station, and capture equipment are co-located, the timing offset of CDMA sequences captured after the initial RNG-RSP should be equal to the timing adjust value passed from the base station to the mobile station. However, this was not the case in practice. The timing offset value was consistently greater than the timing adjust value, which can be seen from a co-located capture in Figure 6. The base station instructed the mobile station to transmit 47 samples early (with reference to the frame structure received from the base station) in the RNG-RSP message (Figure 6a), but the subsequent CDMA sequence sent by the mobile station was only 29 samples early (Figure 6b). This timing bias must be removed in order to determine the correct time t_1 at which the start of the CDMA sequence reached the capture equipment, and is given by the expression

$$t_1 = t_{1L} - \frac{N_{C_bias}}{F_s}, \quad (5)$$

where N_{C_bias} is the timing offset bias of the capture equipment.

The one-way propagation delay between the capture equipment and base station

$$T_{prop_C} = \frac{d_{BS_C}}{c}, \quad (6)$$

where d_{BS_C} is the calculated distance between the base station and the collector in meters based on their known locations. The one-way propagation delay between the mobile station and base station based on the captured timing adjust value in the RNG-RSP message using

$$T_{prop_MS} = \frac{N_{TA} - N_{TA_bias}}{2F_s}. \quad (7)$$

In order to view the start time of the frame containing the CDMA sequence t_{0L} from the perspective of the base station, denoted t_2 , the propagation delay between the capture location and base station must be removed using

$$t_2 = t_{0L} - T_{prop_C}. \quad (8)$$

(a)

Message List All		
Name	Start Time	Timing Offset
Frame	0001.52	
MOB_PAG-ADV	0001.83	
Frame	0006.52	
Frame	0011.52	
Frame	0016.52	
Frame	0021.52	
RNG-RSP	0021.83	
Frame	0026.52	
MOB_PAG-ADV	0026.83	
Frame	0031.52	
CDMA	0034.61	-29
Frame	0036.52	

(b)

Figure 6. Example of a RNG-RSP message (a) and the corresponding CDMA ranging code adjustment (b) in which the base station timing adjust and capture equipment timing offset do not match.

The downlink sub-frame time, the transmit-to-receive transition gap, and ranging code time symbol reference must all be taken into account in the calculation of the time the CDMA sequence should begin:

$$t_3 = t_2 + (N_{DL} + N_{SC})T_s + T_{TTG} \quad (9)$$

where N_{DL} is the number of symbols allocated for downlink transmission, N_{SC} is the time symbol reference (from the RNG-RSP message), T_s is the symbol time, and T_{TTG} is the transmit/receive transition gap time. The estimated time the CDMA sequence was sent by the mobile is given by

$$t_4 = t_3 + T_{prop_MS}. \quad (10)$$

Finally, the difference between the adjusted CDMA capture time t_1 and the estimated time the CDMA sequence was sent by the mobile station t_4 yields an estimate of the propagation time between the mobile station and the capture location and the distance can be calculated as

$$d_{c_MS} = c(t_1 - t_4) \quad (11)$$

which is the radius of a timing ring centered about the capture location.

IV. VALIDATION

This research proceeded using a two-phased approach consisting of experimentation and simulation. The first phase was field experimentation. The results of which then supplied the input for the second phase.

A. Experimentation

We used an IEEE 802.16e-2005 compliant Alcatel-Lucent system operating with a bandwidth of 10 MHz. The network consisted of three base stations deployed outdoors, one base station deployed indoors, and one mobile station. The network timing adjust bias was determined using the indoor base station, and multiple network entry exchanges between the mobile station and base stations were captured outdoors. The combination of network bias and initial ranging process captures provided the requisite inputs to test the accuracy of the proposed geolocation. The capture equipment used was Sanjole's WaveJudge.

In order to determine the timing adjust bias for this network, we captured 20 trials of the initial network entry process. The average timing adjust value was found to be -45.9 (rounded to -46 for post processing). The average difference between the timing offset calculated by the WaveJudge and base station timing adjust was 17 samples, which was recorded as the WaveJudge timing offset bias for use in the post processing algorithm. The WaveJudge was configured to capture the downlink and uplink on separate physical ports with the omni-directional antenna connected to the downlink and the directional antenna connected to the uplink.

From multiple captures, the mean error was found to be 85.06 meters, and the standard deviation was 78.11 meters. The first seven captures were collected while the mobile station was entering the network through Base Station 1, and the second eight captures were collected while the mobile station was entering the network through Base Station 2. The timing adjust bias and timing offset bias used during post processing were 46 and 17, respectively, based on experimental determination.

B. Simulation Model

A schematic diagram of the simulation model can be seen in Figure 7. Random locations for the base station, mobile station and capture equipment are selected within established bounds in a two-dimensional Cartesian plane. The initial ranging process is simulated based on the symbol

parameters, frame parameters, and true distances. The outputs of the ranging process are a timing adjust between the base station and mobile station, a CDMA frame start time, and a CDMA sequence arrival time. Next, timing rings are generated and a position estimate for the mobile station is calculated. The error of the distance between the true mobile station location and the position estimate was calculated.

Figure 7. General model for sparse environment geolocation in WiMAX.

C. Simulation Results

We conducted simulations to compare the geolocation accuracy of a three-base station, two-base station, and one-base station scenario.

The three-base station simulation is similar to the schematic presented in Figure 7 for an area of 100 km^2 . The geometry of the timing rings can result in up to six fixes. The distance is calculated between all combinations of the fix fixes, and the three fixes with the smallest sum of the norms (i.e., the tightest group of fixes) between them are designated as the selected fixes. We applied a fix membership factor, a percentage used to determine if one of the three selected fixes should also be discarded. The membership factor empirically selected for this simulation was 40%.

The position values of the selected fixes are averaged to arrive at the final position estimate. Additionally, constraints were placed on the random locations of the base stations in order to reflect the dispersion which is likely in a deployed network. The range of possible position values for each base station can be seen in Table IV. The mobile station position was randomly placed in the 100 km^2 space. The mean error was 24.81 m with a standard deviation of 15.24 m.

The two-base station simulation is similar to the three-base station scenario. The initial ranging section of the simulation only generates two timing adjusts and their corresponding timing rings. A maximum of two fixes may be

generated based on the geometry of the timing rings, so no form of fix selection and averaging to determine a final fix is required; however, we are left with an ambiguity problem in the case of two fixes. This is handled by automatically selecting the fix closest to the mobile station position for the error calculation; thus, the error results of the simulation represent the best case scenario. The random positioning of the base stations is also constrained as in the three-base station simulation, and the mobile station position is still entirely random. The mean error was 43.31 m with a standard deviation of 52.45 m.

TABLE I. THREE BASE STATION POSITION CONSTRAINTS

	X-Coordinate Range	Y-Coordinate Range
<i>Base Station 1</i>	[0–4500] meters	[0–4500] meters
<i>Base Station 2</i>	[5500–10000] meters	[0–4500] meters
<i>Base Station 3</i>	[2500–7500] meters	[5500–10000] meters
<i>Mobile Station</i>	[0–10000] meters	[0–10000] meters

The one-base station simulation follows the model in Figure 7 with no deviation. The mean error was 82.44 m with a standard deviation of 76.67 m.

The three simulation scenarios presented lend themselves to comparison in terms of their measured probability density functions (PDF) utilizing MATLAB’s *dfittool*. The aim is to determine the probability distribution that makes a set of observed data most likely.

A comparison of the PDFs generated for each simulation scenario can be seen in Figure 8. The peak height and the two-dimensional error value at which the peak occurs correlates directly to the number of base stations involved in the position estimate. The three-base station scenario has a consistent low error, while the one-base station scenario is characterized by greater error with more variation. The mean for each distribution is the same as the mean in the corresponding histograms. The λ values are 90.1128, 34.6751, and 39.8266 for the one-base station, two-base station, and three-base station simulations, respectively.

V. CONCLUSIONS

A method of geolocation based on an IEEE 802.16 compliant network deployment capable of providing an independent position estimate from a single base station was proposed, simulated, and experimentally validated. We provided a proof-of-concept for the geolocation method in a close range scenario via experimentation in an IEEE 802.16 network. We also developed the simulation model based on the experimental data in order to provide justification for a mean error that is consistent with close range experimental results when the method is employed across a realistically sized wireless network cell. The single base station geolocation method developed extends the idea presented in [7] by generating a position estimate for the mobile station with respect to the positions of the base station and capture

equipment locations. The method capitalizes on the unencrypted initial ranging exchange between the base station and mobile station.

Figure 8. Inverse Gaussian PDF comparison for the simulation error.

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